

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D8.2

MES-CoBraD Validation Framework

January 2022

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UPS	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
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UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
DoD	Definition of Done
MES-CoBraD	Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders
PO	Product Owner
UAT	User Acceptance Testing

Executive Summary

The MES-CoBraD Framework Evaluation and System Validation deliverable documents the evaluation framework and validation methodology of the MES-CoBraD Platform and Pilot Protocol, defining the various practices for obtaining feedback from end-users and including a set of test-cases to be executed by the end-users.

The final MES-CoBraD Expert System will have multiple benefits for the diagnostics and treatments of complex brain disorders. In terms of diagnostics, the platform will output information that can help inform the diagnosis given to patients by clinicians, and in turn, the advice, guidance, and appropriate treatments for that action. The Platform's wide array of outputs will be of interest to a vast range of different researchers, involved mainly in medical and social research, but not limited to these fields. The Platform will aim to empower patients and caregivers by helping them to have a greater understanding of their condition, offering more participation in the medical process, with the ultimate aim of improving their health outcomes.

To assess the Platform's validity to the above goals, we will use a Framework Evaluation feedback approach. This is composed of high-level subjective user experience feedback from stakeholders that either used the Platform or applied/participated in the Pilot Protocol. These reflect how the Platform high-level outputs impact the respective stakeholder practices and needs, as well as how the multidisciplinary diagnostic protocol served unmet needs in clinical and research practice.

Four stakeholder groups will be involved in the Framework Evaluation feedback. Clinicians and researchers will be involved in the collection of feedback on the Platform's impact of output, Pilot implementation, Analysis and use of the Platform's modules, validating the quality of obtained Real World Datasets and the interpretation of analytical results. Patients and caregivers will be involved in Platform's impact of output and Pilot implementation feedback.

Additionally, to test the methodology of the Platform we will obtain objective feedback on the MES-CoBraD Platform use through test cases towards examining whether the Platform modules are used as-intended, as well as obtaining structured step-by-step feedback from stakeholders on their ability to use specific Platform features.

The test cases will cover all the meaningful functionalities that will be required during real-world usage of the Platform. Different group of testers will be assigned to each test case. The selection will be done from a real-world target audience and won't include people involved in the development process to avoid any kind of bias. Test Cases will be focused on checking system functionality, especially seeing that the system and its components perform according to requirements and specifications.

The data collected will allow for an overall assessment and evaluation of MES-CoBraD from a user's perspective. The feedback obtained on the implementation, operation, and execution of the Pilot Protocol will help formulate methodological adoption guidelines for the further exploitation and utilization of the Project's Platform.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The MES-CoBraD Framework Evaluation and System Validation deliverable documents the evaluation framework and validation methodology of the MES-CoBraD Platform and Pilot Protocol, defining the various practices for obtaining feedback from end-users and including a set of test-cases to be executed by the end-users.

The data collected will allow for an overall assessment and evaluation of MES-CoBraD from a user's perspective. The evaluation activities will be focused both on the correct application of the MES-CoBraD Platform and on its impact on CoBraD management. Furthermore, the feedback obtained on the implementation, operation, and execution of the Pilot Protocol will help formulate methodological adoption guidelines for the further exploitation and utilisation of the Project's Platform.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The current deliverable is structured as a report in two sections. The Framework Evaluation and the System Validation and User Acceptance.

Framework Evaluation feedback is focused on the practices in obtaining high-level subjective user experience feedback from stakeholders that either used the Platform or apply the Pilot Protocol. These reflect how the Platform high-level outputs impact the respective stakeholder practices and needs, ranging from user-interface features, advanced analytics modules, visualisation and interpretation of results, and ease of quality validation of Real-World Datasets. Furthermore, on a clinical-research level, Pilot Protocol participation and implementation feedback focuses on how the multidisciplinary diagnostic protocol served unmet needs in clinical and research practice, as well as whether there were elements that interfered with the feasibility of the Protocol.

System Validation and User Acceptance outlines the approaches in obtaining objective feedback on the MES-CoBraD Platform use through test cases towards examining whether the Platform modules are used as-intended, as well as obtaining structured step-by-step feedback from stakeholders on their ability to use specific Platform features. Specific top-level test cases are first outlined, followed by approaches in identifying testers, timing of when the test cases will be assessed and feedback obtained, and, finally, processes in validating changes according to the specific feedback obtained.

2. FRAMEWORK EVALUATION

2.1 IMPACT OF PLATFORM OUTPUT

The final MES-CoBraD Expert System will have multiple benefits for the diagnostics and treatments of complex brain disorders. In this section we specify how different groups of stakeholders may use and be affected by the outputs of the platform, more accurately and precisely outlining the strengths and uses of the MES-CoBraD platform.

2.1.1 CLINICIANS

Clinicians work directly with patients and are, therefore, in a position to be assisted by the Platform's diagnostic and therapeutic outputs. In terms of diagnostics, the platform will output information that can help inform the diagnosis given to patients, and in turn, the advice, guidance, and appropriate treatments for that action. Resources of clinicians may be limited, in terms of time, material resources and knowledge: Not every clinician has expertise in the field of complex brain disorders and the platform will be a base of expert knowledge to help clinicians. It is important that clinicians are trained to understand the platform and use it in the correct way when treating patients, seeing it as a tool to work with not a system to parrot.

2.1.2 RESEARCHERS

The platform's outputs will be of interest to a vast range of different researchers, conducting various types of research, chiefly medical and societal research, but not exhaustive to these fields. For example, some may be interested in studying how the outputs of the platform affect the accuracy and speed of diagnosis, and the uptake of treatment. In other words, how the platform affects outcomes for patients. Others may be interested in how the platform changes the work of clinicians and how they incorporate this into their work. Through this type of work the platform will be open to scrutiny and ultimately can be improved. Therefore, it is important for researchers to have access to the platform's outputs, and a clear understanding of how it works as a tool for offering medical knowledge and assistance. As a result, further feedback on the platform will be collected through this research, improving its outputs, and then streamlining any future research activities.

2.1.3 PATIENTS

By granting patients access to the expert system it empowers them to have a greater understanding of their condition, offering more agency in the medical process, with the ultimate aim of improving their health outcomes. In addition, it will give them a broader set of opinions and information, widening their base of information beyond their first-hand care network. The impact of the platform's outputs will greatly depend on the patient themselves and the medical setting they find themselves in. Despite this, the platform will provide every patient access to information allowing them insight and understanding of the procedures which medical decisions would be based upon. This transparency would facilitate more patient-centred care and patient-centred decision making. Overall, it is clear that the diagnostic and therapeutic aspects of the platform will be the most important for this group.

2.1.4 CAREGIVERS

The platform's outputs for caregivers will have a similar affect as those for patients, centring mainly on diagnostics. Giving caregivers access to the same information as patients ensures that they are able to support their treatment properly, and approach care from the same page as the individual being cared for.

2.2 PILOT IMPLEMENTATION

The final MES-CoBraD expert system is grounded on a curated list of multimodal data that provides both clinical and research-based relevant information. The list of data, that expands from cognitive test evaluation, neurophysiological data, biochemical biomarkers and/or imaging data, is based on a Scientific Protocol, which is agreed by the members of the consortium. Nevertheless, the proposed Scientific Protocol might not tackle every stakeholder need. Thus, feedback from clinicians, researchers, patients and caregivers must be a powerful tool to improve the scientific protocol of the MES-CoBraD study.

2.2.1 CLINICIANS

Clinicians working directly with the MES-CoBraD platform will be able to input patient-related information that will result into a system-based diagnostic and/or therapeutics recommendation. Nevertheless, there might be some important metrics, that the clinician considers relevant for a correct diagnosis that are not present in the platform. The clinicians will be able to provide feedback on those missing input-fields. Volunteers representing a variety of clinicians in different sub-specializations (e.g., dementia or sleep) will provide high-level feedback on the importance and relevance of the included multimodal multi-source items and suggest for extension/modification of some of them, if necessary. The obtained feedback will be reviewed and recommended changes identified, which will result into modifications when considered relevant for the overall platform's correct functionality.

2.2.2 RESEARCHERS

Similarly to Clinicians, Researchers working directly with the MES-CoBraD platform will be allowed to introduce several multimodal data into the platform. Nevertheless, not the entire span of options are included in the platform, and researcher might miss important data-types or inputs (e.g complementary cognitive scores or multi-domain imaging acquisitions).

Volunteers representing researcher stakeholders will provide high-level feedback on the scientific protocol usefulness through questionnaires and propose extensions/modifications to the protocol. Such proposals will be evaluated and if required, integrated into the platform.

2.2.3 PATIENTS AND CAREGIVERS

Patients and caregivers will use the MES-CoBraD platform to participate in clinical and neuropsychological evaluations, and to fill patient-related questionnaires. Receiving feedback on the easiness to perform the different tests, how difficult is to understand and answer them without the direct guidelines of the clinicians, its crucial for a good working of the platform.

Volunteers representing patients and caregivers' stakeholders, will provide high-level feedback on the difficulty to answer the different tests, and how comfortable they felt using the platform for this propose.

2.3 ANALYSIS AND USE OF MODULES

2.3.1 CLINICIANS

Clinicians who use the Platform will be able to collect, review and upload data, and analyse these data through the Platform's modules. The analysis will inform the clinicians in making diagnoses of deep phenotyping and guiding them on the next steps in a diagnostic pathway and/or appropriate treatments based on the available data (Expert System module). By assessing the modules of the Platform, volunteers representing clinician

stakeholders will provide high-level feedback on the quality and usefulness of the analytic modules (Advanced Analytics and Expert System) primarily through questionnaires. These questionnaires will try to determine the ease of using modules, the completeness of modules, the estimated validity and relevance of the analytic output of modules, and how they were implemented in clinical scenarios. Feedback on questions will be in both quantitative (responses ranging 1-5) and qualitative format (free text).

2.3.2 RESEARCHERS.

Researchers will have the opportunity to analyse data using the Platform's Advanced Analytics modules, and also receive pilot guidance in pursuing specific analytic processes to answer a hypothesis through the Expert System. The analytics modules will help researchers in testing their hypothesis through pre-defined statistical and heuristic analyses. By assessing the modules of the Platform, volunteers representing researcher stakeholders will provide top-level feedback on the quality and usefulness of the analytic modules through questionnaires. These questionnaires will try to determine the ease of using modules, the completeness of modules, the estimated validity and relevance of the analytic output of modules, and how they were implemented in research settings. Feedback on questions will be in both quantitative (responses ranging 1-5) and qualitative format (free text).

Feedback provided by both clinicians and researchers who use the analytics modules will be reviewed and recommended changes identified, allowing for Platform modifications to serve user needs. This process will be core to the MES-CoBraD Platform sustainability in continuously obtaining feedback to improve the analytic module features.

2.4 VALIDATING THE QUALITY OF OBTAINED REAL WORLD DATASETS

Ensuring the data on the MES-CoBraD Platform is of high quality is central to achieving the goals of the project. Therefore, creating systems within the Platform to check data for formatting, structure, completeness, accuracy and consistency is critical.

2.4.1 CLINICIANS

The Platform will verify data format and structure at the point they are inserted into the system (regardless of how that data is input, e.g., direct-to-platform, manual data entry), allowing for the identification of data that is improperly formatted or structured and notifying the relevant user for follow up. The Platform will allow for data cleaning and validation processes, including the identification of duplicate records, implausible and outlier values, missing or corrupt data.

Feedback from users in the form of questionnaires (as described in 2.3.2) will contribute to the refinement of the platform's data entry processes, including the user interface, and will also be used to better understand challenges encountered with 'paper-to-platform' or manual data entry, including time required, ease of data entry and other feedback relevant to ensuring data quality.

Automated data checking/validation will be performed where possible. Where the same variables are uploaded into the platform multiple times (e.g., patient date of birth), responses will be automatically checked for alignment. Where there are discrepancies, the system will notify the relevant user for follow up.

2.4.2 RESEARCHERS

Researchers may also be interested in understanding the quality of the data as a whole. Therefore, it would be important to have mechanisms in place to understand data quality at both the individual and wider study

population level. This includes the ability to assess completeness: The platform will track percent of missing values for any given individual, and percent of records with missing values for a given variable. It also includes the ability to assess accuracy: where possible, known standards or population means/ranges for particular variables could be used as benchmark values against which to identify outlier or implausible data. It also includes the ability to assess consistency or uniformity across participant data: where data over time can be viewed to identify (unexpected) changes in trends or distributions.

Feedback from researchers pertaining to the assessment of data quality will be obtained to inform the refinement of the Platform.

2.5 INTERPRETATION OF ANALYTICAL RESULTS

2.5.1 CLINICIANS

Clinicians working directly with patients will follow core steps for data interpretation when using the MES-CoBraD platform. Thus, the interpretation of the output obtained from data analytics will help in both diagnostic and therapeutics. Firstly, clinicians will assemble the information that is needed to perform these procedures by answering a series of questions based on preliminary findings. Therefore, building the knowledge to develop findings and conclusions that will provide recommendations to be followed. The originated findings will also be related to previous reported results, known standards and guidelines in order to execute differential diagnosis considering distinct CoBraD with overlap of similar symptoms as well as the stratification of patients suffering from the same disorder. Once the MES-CoBraD platform is based on the collaboration between clinicians with deep specialisation in distinct areas, these professionals will contribute for the verification, addition and correction of the interpretation of the statement results summarising the important points of the monitoring program provided by the platform. Thus, these findings will contribute to come up with conclusions by helping in the formulation of more accurate interpretations that thoroughly observe the trends and patterns or lack of patterns in the analysed data. It is important to notice that, in order to provide correct recommendations based on findings, the defined conclusions should be related back to the questions established at the beginning by the clinician to the monitoring program on the platform. Based on the interpretation of the submitted and analysed data, the platform-algorithm will provide recommendations in two forms: one form provides action suggested to be taken by the clinician in a particular CoBraD. In circumstances where action to be taken is not yet sustained enough, the platform-algorithm will suggest *gathering further information and/or complementary examinations* that seem essential to continue running the algorithm in order to provide a precise diagnosis. Complementary, when a diagnose is obtained, therapeutics to be applied given specific conditions will be suggested to the clinician by the algorithm.

2.5.2 RESEARCHERS

Researchers using the MES-CoBraD platform will perform data interpretation through the review process of the analytics output. This will aim to assign meaning to the results obtained, therefore striving to reach relevant conclusions. The inferences on the relations being studied will contribute to a better understanding of perturbed molecular and systemic mechanisms associated to particular CoBraD and their pathophysiology. Thus, a more insightful understanding of alterations associated with distinct CoBraD will allow the deep phenotyping of distinct disorders.

For researchers, data interpretation is built-on data advanced analysis and outputs, which include the process of ordering, categorizing, manipulating and summarising the data to answer the research questions. In order

to aid the process, the platform will have available qualitative and quantitative methods as well as visualisation techniques for data interpretation to be applied by the researchers when using the platform. Moreover, with the data analysis tools and machine learning techniques accessible through the platform, data interpretation considering CoBraD and associated co-variables will provide new insightful understanding of the complexity underlying these disorders. Thus, these interpretations will contribute to the formulation of new research questions towards a more precise diagnosis of CoBraD by helping the elaboration of data-driven decisions. Additionally, the extensive understanding of involved cellular and physiologic pathways to CoBraD might enable the suggestion of breakthrough personalised therapeutics as well as the repurpose of already available medical drugs. Among other functions, the MES-CoBraD platform works as a repository for an extensive collection of patients' metadata of interest related to CoBraD, which contributes for the determination of patients' susceptibility for developing CoBraD given their clinical history and health status. Additionally, data interpretation might include uncovering of associations between distinct CoBraD and patients' sleep patterns.

3. SYSTEM VALIDATION AND USER ACCEPTANCE

In technological system testing, there are usually two objectives for which such tests can be carried out: *verification* and *validation*. Verification testing refers to checking the conformity of the system (or its components) behaviour to the defined specifications. In other words, the question to be answered by the verification process is: *was the system built right?* Verification is performed throughout the development phase, before validation, to ensure that the system features and behaviour correspond to formal requirements. Validation testing is usually carried out by professional testers employed by the developer organization.

Validation is carried out at the end of the development process to check that the system corresponds to user expectations. The question to be answered by validation is: *was the right system built?* This process is usually carried out by users/testers working for the beneficiary/client organization of the system.

In the case of MES-CoBraD Project there is some apparent overlap between T7.4 System Verification and Validation and T8.3 Implementation of the Multidisciplinary Protocol CoBraD& Pilots Evaluation. While T7.4 is to some extent concerned with Validation per its title, the task description focuses mainly on verification testing. We take this to mean that while T7.4 will be mainly focused on verification as part of the development and integration processes, there will be some concern for validation in T7.4 especially with regards to planning and ensuring that the conditions are in place for the validation process. However, the validation process will be carried out in T8.2 (and WP8 more broadly). It is important that partners (and task leaders) collaborate between these two tasks and work packages especially as some activities and instruments (such as test cases) will be shared.

As far as the development methodology is concerned, three models have been investigated to determine whether they are in line with the MES-CoBraD solution development methodology: Waterfall, V-Model and Agile Model.

The principles and practices specific to Agile and V-Model fit to the needs of testing in MES-CoBraD. This comes from the complexity of the system which lies in the difficulty of a unitary approach for the interoperability of the various tools with different maturity levels (TRL) based on diverse technologies and complex architectural solutions.

3.1 APPLICABLE STANDARDS

Another demanding part of the testing approach is to address the existing standards, and more particularly by matching the methodology and concepts of the testing procedure with the rules and stipulations of the standards.

Two IEEE sets of standards are applicable for the testing stage in MES-CoBraD: **IEEE 829-2008 – IEEE Standard for Software and System Test Documentation** and **ISO-IEC-IEEE 29119 – Software and system engineering – Software testing**.

The first applicable standard, IEEE 829 – 2008 is a comprehensive guide that specifies a common framework for planning the testing activities [focusing on software test documentation. Most of the rules and stipulations of this standard were taken over by the new ISO-IEC-IEEE 29119 standard, in Part 3: Test Documentation.]

The new international software testing standard ISO-IEC-IEEE 29119, with its latest part published in 2016, aims at replacing the existing standards for software testing: IEEE 829 for test documentation, IEEE 1008 for unit testing, BS 7925-1 for vocabulary of terms in software testing and BS 7925-2 for software component testing

3.2 TESTING MODEL

Compatibility with the above-mentioned standards was the basis for choosing the two conceptual development models applicable in MES-CoBraD – V- model and Agile.

The first model (V-Model) provides an applicable option regarding how the testing levels are organized in the standard IEEE 829 – 2008 (Unit (component) testing, Integration testing, System testing and Acceptance testing) and is compliant with our testing approach. The second model (Agile model) is an applicable option due to the agile iterative cycle of development-testing style applied within MES-CoBraD, and it meets the requirement of continuous improvement of software based on a rapid feedback from testing.

The V-Model used, based on SIMAVI Software development Procedures¹ is depicted in the next figure:

Figure 1 – V-Model

¹ SIMaVI-P-QS-03-04

The appropriate agile testing techniques are specific to the following Agile testing areas:

- A1: Technology-facing tests that support the team
- A2: Business-facing tests that support the team
- A3: Business-facing tests that critique the product (focused on the acceptance of the product)
- A4: Technology-facing tests that critique the product (focused on the performance criteria of the product).

Analyzing the specific features of each testing area, two of the agile testing areas were mainly addressed within, and tailored to this particular stage of MES-CoBraD project implementation: A2 and A3.

The particularity of this type of testing is given by the conceptual focusing of testing on feature – *feature driven testing*, applying the same approach as for the feature driven development (FDD) [Error! Reference source not found.].

The testing process proposed for MES-CoBraD, based on agile methodology, and specifically, feature driven testing, takes into account the specific methodological requirements of the project and the conceptual architectural design of the MES-CoBraD toolkit.

The outcomes of the testing process include documents referring to:

- What was tested (using test cases) and test failures (bugs)
- Which bugs caused failures and when they can be addressed

Specific tasks for each team are registered in Jira - a specific application for issue tracking and general project management features.

The Agile model considered is depicted in the next figure [AGILE]

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Figure 2 – AGILE Methodology

UAT are not strictly related to Agile methodologies, indeed the Agile manifesto doesn't explicitly mention them or the best practices to execute them; it remains on a higher-level, simply saying:

“Our highest priority is to satisfy the customer through early and continuous delivery of valuable software”².

This means that the UAT are a more-than-welcome tool to ensure that the end-users are satisfied about the output produced during a sprint.

Since SCRUM is a framework to implement Agile methodology, not a detailed guide, the teams are enabled to interpret it according to project specificities and peculiarities. About UAT there are then several ways of thinking; the three most relevant are:

- › The UAT execution is part of the Definition of Done (DoD)
- › The UAT execution is part of the Sprint Review
- › The UAT are not part of the sprint at all and are executed in parallel

The three approaches are different from each other, because of the impact on the sprint execution and also on the user story lifecycle.

In particular, the inclusion of the UAT in the DoD ensures that the software is always compliant with the end-users needs, even when it's in the staging phase; but, at the same time, could have as a consequence that an already completed user story, even if tested and compliant with the original specification, could be rejected from the end-users and not be considered shippable in the current sprint. This would negatively affect the velocity of the team and the ability to address the sprint goal, causing an increment of the technical debt across the sprints and, in general a worst performance of the team.

The second approach, on the contrary, ensures that, if a user-story is tested, compliant with the original specification and approved by the Product Owner(PO), could be considered completed and shippable. Indeed, it will be analysed during the Sprint Review. In this phase, the end-users will perform the UAT with the goal of providing feedbacks on the produced output and, as a result, create new entries in the product backlog that will be part of the next sprints, without negatively affecting the just ended iteration. This approach could cause, as side effect, a longer duration of the Sprint Review meeting, reducing the effectiveness of the meeting itself.

The third approach executes the UAT completely outside the sprints loop, ensuring that the impact on the sprint execution is totally removed. According to this approach, the PO will accept the user-stories during the Sprint Review and the related features will be deployed in the staging environment. Now, asynchronously, the end-users (domain experts) can schedule a UAT session to validate the increment and label the software as *“ready to be released in production”* and/or enrich the product backlog with feedbacks and correction. This last approach requires that the PO is domain aware and has a good comprehension of the end-user needs, otherwise the risk is to increment the amount of required re-works.

In the context of MES-CoBraD project the consortium decided to adopt the third up-mentioned approach.

² <https://agilemanifesto.org/iso/en/principles.html>

According to this choice, the consortium will agree and share internally a calendar for the UAT sessions. These sessions will involve at least:

- › one representative of the development team,
- › one representative of the testing team
- › and the Product Owner that will act as a moderator.

Such meetings will take place asynchronously respect the Sprint executions and whose goal will be the feeding of the Product Backlog with further improvement of the already developed software.

The following diagram shows the steps in conducting the UAT sessions.

Figure 3 - UAT Sessions lifecycle

The UAT Planning step has been done to decide the UAT execution strategy for the entire duration of the project. This document is also part of the outcome of the UAT planning step.

Once the planning has been completed, the test cases must be designed to cover all the meaningful functionalities that are likely to happen during real-world usage of the platform. The section 3.1 presents top-level test cases that are based on epics and that will be broke down in more fine-grained test cases at each UAT session. The output will be a document that presents the Test case according to the template available in ANNEX I :

According to the test cases designed and their peculiarities, a group of testers will be assigned to each test case. The selection will be done from a real-world target audience and won't include people involved in the development process to avoid any kind of bias. In general, the tester selection strategy is presented in section 3.3

Once the first increment will be released in the staging environment, the UAT sessions will start to take place according to their specific calendar. The test cases selection criteria are presented in more details in section 3.3.

All the functionalities that have been accepted during the sessions will be labelled as “Ready for Release”; those that have been rejected will be re-planned in the future sprints for bug-fixes and then will be evaluated again. The strategy to acquire and implement the collected feedback is presented in section 3.4.

3.3 SELECTING TESTERS

User acceptance testing rely on end users' commitment to conduct a thorough evaluation of all the functionalities of the platform. Experts overseeing the technical side of the platform development play a key role in shaping UAT cycles and obviously interpreting the results. However, users from the business side play an equally significant role as they are the only ones who know exactly what the platform should look like in their day-to-day practice.

Provided that test cases shall be defined based on different epics, the most relevant group of testers for each case must be selected, to not only secure the technical adequacy of the platform but also to be able to verify the results. To facilitate the selection, we classified the end users based on relevant stakeholder groups identified in D7.1., in the following six (6):

- › Clinicians
- › Researchers
- › Patients
- › Caregivers
- › System Administrators
- › Security engineers

Since the user acceptance testing will be conducted using the SCRUM framework, thus repeating each test at different maturity levels of the project, we consider end user involvement to be a very crucial and demanding process. User acceptance testing requires significant effort from the end users and their constant participation might lead to fatigue, jeopardising the results. To streamline and facilitate the process, in some iterations we intent to emulate some of the stakeholder groups using members from different groups who have the necessary knowledge and skillset required. For instance, Patients and caregivers may be emulated by clinicians/researchers if necessary.

The number of testers participating in each test will depend on how broad its scope is and how flexibly the actions described within can be executed. Additionally, the complexity of the components involved with the test case will also affect the testers' numbers.

3.4 DEFINING TOP-LEVEL TEST CASES BASED ON EPICS

The test cases themselves will be initially based on user epics, that describe generally all the actions the users can take while using our applications. Since these epics only loosely describe the actions users take, they will be further broken down in more fine-grained test cases at each UAT iteration. These epics will be well-defined during the actual system validation process. Here we present a first draft for those test cases based on epics and the user groups that will participate in each test case.

Table 1 Top-level test cases

Test Case: Data Entry, Importing	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Users can store the RWD, such as patient data on the platform cloud and have it available and accessible on their account. In addition, they can create questionnaires, which users will fill in.	Clinicians, Researchers, Patients, Caregivers

Test Case: Data Anonymisation	
Description	User Stakeholder groups

When inputting data users, should be able to easily anonymise the data they added to the platform, so they can be made available to third parties.	Researchers
--	-------------

Test Case: Data Integration, Preparation and Harmonisation	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Users can harmonise uploaded datasets, define their metadata and setup their license, controlling who has access to them. They should also be able to grant access to the dataset to a third party, at a separate point. This functionality will also include the platform defined questionnaires.	Researchers

Test Case: Process definition and implementation	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Users can define and test research workflows, that can represent diagnostic or treatment protocols. These workflows will involve other tools, such as data analytics, AI, visualisation, reporting tools and their execution will be partially automated. This will allow to test and measure their performance.	Clinicians, Researchers

Test Case: Data Analytics and Visualisations	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Users can perform analytics health-related data including MRIs, EEG tests and other patient data directly on the platform. Visualizations, figures and graphs can be produced by the platform, using these data and configured by the users.	Clinicians, Researchers

Test Case: Adaptive Training algorithm definition and implementation	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Users can define diagnostic protocol /give clinical recommendations with AI, train those algorithm using provided datasets and apply the algorithms to different datasets.	Clinicians, Researchers, Patients, Caregivers

Test Case: Reporting	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
I would like to receive reports that sum my health data and compare it to	Clinicians, Researchers

other users, as well as recommendations for follow up. and Automated report /message generator
--

Test Case: System Security Validation	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Implementing security testing, ensure data safety and production readiness status of the platform	Security Engineers

Test Case: System Configuration	
Description	User Stakeholder groups
Setting up master accounts, designating site admins with various degrees of permissions, granting users access to datasets and platform functions.	System Administrators

3.5 SELECTION AND TIMING OF TEST CASE EXECUTION AND DOCUMENTATION

Once defined the top-level User Acceptance Test cases (in section 3.2), a more fine-grained list of UAT will be created and designed. These test cases will be listed in a document available to the entire consortium that will be continuously updated and maintained.

At the beginning of each SCRUM sprint, during the Planning, the UAT cases will be selected along with the User Stories and technical tasks to address in the upcoming weeks. All the tasks in the sprint should have a reference to one or more UAT chosen according to which is the platform functionalities affected by such a task. Only in case of tasks that do not have any impact on the end-user experience could be excluded from the assignment of the related UAT cases.

Once the sprint ends and the functionalities are released in the staging environment, a UAT session will take place according to what stated in section 3. This session won't affect the just completed sprint that will be considered concluded.

During such UAT session, the tester will compile a report compliant with the template in ANNEX II : and will share it with the development team that will analyse it (at most) during the subsequent Sprint Planning or, better, during a backlog grooming meeting.

After the development team report analysis, the feedback will be transformed into technical tasks in the product backlog. The Feedback acquisition and implementation will be subject of discussion in the following section 3.6.

3.6 ACQUIRING AND IMPLEMENTING FEEDBACK

This section focuses on the use of questionnaires for obtaining feedback from piloting participants. We establish here the broad principles and alternatives of assessment by questionnaire of the MES-CoBraD System. Questionnaires, in the context of software testing, are an alternative of obtaining feedback from testers/users, complementary to Test Cases and Scenarios. Test Cases are focused on checking system functionality, especially seeing that the system and its components perform according to requirements and

specifications. Questionnaires can and should focus on alternate issues such as usability, relevance, usefulness, compliance etc.

There are two broad types of questionnaires that can be applied in the context of software testing:

1. *Tool Focused Feedback Questionnaire(s)*: this is the main instrument in our box. This type of questionnaire is focused on users/pilots' feedback on a tool/component after they have used that tool. They provide tool specific feedback on issues such as enumerated above: usability, relevance, etc. This questionnaire type is applied at the end of testing sessions, after the user has had the chance to use (test) the specific tools.
2. *General Questionnaire about Users' and their Attitudes toward relevant Technologies*. This is a general questionnaire applied usually at a user's/participant's entry in the testing/piloting process. It collects general information about a user's background (user role, position, education, gender, etc.) and their (baseline) attitudes/perceptions about relevant technologies. This type of questionnaire offers the opportunity to understand better users' background and attitudes toward technologies. In addition, this may present an opportunity for scientific research and communication of technology adoption/acceptance.

While (2) above is an option to be further considered, we focus our discussion below on (1) Tool Focuses Feedback Questionnaire as it most directly answers the scope of this chapter. We elaborate on (2) at the end of this chapter.

3.6.1 SCOPE AND GRANULARITY OF QUESTIONNAIRE

The issue of scope or granularity of the Tool Focused Feedback Questionnaire refers to what is the feedback collected about. At the lowest level of granularity, the questionnaire could be applied for each functionality/requirement of the system and its components. However, with a total number of over 100 requirements for the whole system, this level of granularity would be completely impractical and may make the testing process slow and cumbersome. At the other end, the highest level of granularity, the questionnaire could be applied for the whole MES-CoBraD System. However, this would lose sight of many details which are specific to each tool and the feedback, if too general, may not be actionable. Therefore, we think that a mid-level of granularity is most appropriate, where we envisage to apply the questionnaire *once per testing session, per component, per user*.

3. Once per testing session: The questionnaire is applied at during or at the testing session after the participants had the chance of using/testing some tools/components of the system. It is thus imperative that in the same testing session both Test Cases are used (for functional testing), and questionnaires are applied for non-functional feedback. This is necessary because if questionnaires are applied at a different time (e.g. significantly later than the testing session such as a next meeting/testing session) the experience with the tools may no longer be fresh in participants' minds.
4. Once per component/tool being tested: The questionnaire is applied separately and repeatedly for each component being tested. As explained, this should provide sufficiently specific feedback related to some (user facing) non-functional features of the tool being tested. This also implies that we will usually attempt to formulate the questions in a general manner such that they are applicable to all tools/components. Only if very specific circumstances require so, we may have component specific questions. It should be noted that this rule may suffer alterations as we develop the questionnaires and plan their application. If piloting scenarios involve often going across components then we may have to accept that questionnaires can be used for multiple components at once (or for parts of components, i.e. only some functionalities combined with parts of other components).

5. **Once per user:** this means that each user/participant fills the questionnaire separately from the others and do not fill as a group.

The criteria above should be interpreted as being able to be combined, usually resulting in multiple questionnaires being filled. For example, if in one testing session there are three components/tools being tested, and 10 participants. This means that each participant fills in 3 questionnaires (once per each component) for a total of 30 questionnaires answered (given that there are 10 participants). Also, if the same component is tested repeatedly in two different testing sessions by (some of) the same participants, they will fill the questionnaire as referring to that component, again in the second session (to reflect the new experience with the same component) – this however should only happen if some significant changes (e.g. bug fixing) have taken place to warrant another testing session by the same participants.

3.6.2 QUESTIONNAIRE RESPONDENTS

Questionnaire respondents (i.e. testers or piloting participants) will usually reflect the user roles as they have been designed in D7.1 (since the user roles have usually been defined following institutional positions of users). They include scientists (researchers), scientist coordinators, clinicians, caregivers, patients. Additional details related to these participants and their selection were provided in 3.3 above.

3.6.3 QUESTIONNAIRE APPLICATION METHOD

Testing participants will self-complete the questionnaires they will read the questions and provide the answers themselves. I.e. usually no operator will read the questions and record the answers for them, however, in exceptional circumstances an operator may provide assistance. The questionnaires will be filled preferably on a computer using a specific software (if possible, at the time of testing, the very tool developed under our project *Questionnaire Builder*). As a backup method, where it may not be possible to fill the questionnaire on a computer, questionnaires shall be printed and filled on paper, then later the answers will be transcribed in an electronic format.

3.6.4 RESULTS ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION

The analysis and evaluation of results must include both Test Case results and Questionnaire Answers. The former are focused on more functional issues encountered in the execution of tests, while the latter are focused on non-functional issues.

Analysis will combine quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis. Quantitative analysis will usually include descriptive univariate statistics such as averages, and distribution of frequencies. Qualitative analysis will focus on identifying specific issues encountered and will serve as a precursor to issue reporting and tracking.

3.6.5 ISSUE REPORTING AND TRACKING

Issue/incident management shall be carried out in a specialized incident management software solution such as JIRA. Piloting participants shall not use JIRA directly but shall use specific incident reporting instruments made available by the consortium (e.g. Excel or Word Test Case reporting forms or online questionnaires). Specialized tester professionals shall use JIRA for reporting incidents as explained below.

3.6.6 ISSUE REPLICATION AND REPORTING

Following the analysis and evaluation of results, testers from the teams of technological partners (each partner for the components they are responsible) shall attempt to replicate the issues reported by participants in

piloting. Based on participants description and professional testers’ replication of the issues these shall be classified and ticketed into the issue management system.

3.6.7 ISSUE CLASSIFICATION

Depending on the type of actions/improvements needed to solve the issues these shall be classified in the following categories:

1. Technical Documentation and Training Issues/Improvements: These are issues that can be solved by better explanation of how to use certain functionalities in either technical documentation or training of participants.
2. Technical Issues: These are issues with the functionality, overall look, or content of the MesCo-BraD System.
3. Other Issues: These are any other type of issues that may have impacted the results of the testing. They may include issues related to the organization of testing sessions, or other issues that may require some kind of action.

Technical Issues may be further classified according to the Table 2 below:

Table 2: Technical Incident Types

No	Type of incident	Description of type
1	Bug	This type of incident depicts a software code problem; this is usually also named “code error”.
2	Improvement	This type of incident should be used whenever a change is necessary in an application, no matter if it is an aspect of Graphical-User-Interface or of a business or functionality component.
3	Assistance	This type of incident depicts a need for technical assistance in using the applications.
4	Task	This type of incident depicts a need for a very specific technical task.
5	New Feature	This type of incident depicts a need for a new development for the existing applications, no matter if there are small, minor changes or new modules.

3.7 VALIDATING CHANGES, USER ACCEPTANCE AND ITERATIVE PROGRESS

With the UAT process clearly defined in the previous sections, the testing can be initiated, addressing any defects, and deciding whether to move ahead to the final acceptance. To make this step optimally efficient, we need flawless communication and balance between testers and developers, with a particular focus on analytical documentation, progress reporting, and defect management.

After each iteration of a test case, we need to ensure that the test case has been executed successfully and the implemented changes sufficiently address any feedback we acquired from previous iterations. This will be achieved through the following checklist.

Table 3 Test and Feedback validation checklist

Test and Feedback validation checklist	
Were all steps of the test run documented?	
Was the acceptance test performed according to the test plan?	
Did the users review the test results?	
Are the services provided by the system in compliance with user requirements?	
Were all defects documented?	
Were all identified defects and issues resolved?	
Did the users judge acceptability in accordance with the predetermined criteria?	

The checklist will be provided by the test conductors after each iteration. If any item in the checklist is not achieved, the issue will be analysed, and the testing process will be paused where necessary. A report shall be drafted presenting the status of the test together with the estimated time and effort required to meet acceptance criteria and recommendations.

Especially in case defects are identified, they should be re-tested, once fixed, as this not only generates user confidence, due to managing a transparent defect process, but also confirms that you are fixing what has been agreed by all. Once all identified defects are fixed, the testing process will be re-initiated, based on test scheduling (Section 3.3) to make sure everything is working properly.

After the process is completed again, a new checklist will be filled in. This is repeated until the final checklist is completed and all the tasks will be marked as completed. When the acceptance criteria are reached and approved by reviewers, the final acceptance decision will be made.

ANNEX I :

User Acceptance Test Cases MES-CoBraD

Section 1 : <Test Suite A>

[Provide a description of what test cases are included in this suite]

<Test A.1>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

1.1 <Test A.2>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

1.2 <Test A.3>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks

Section 2 : <Test Suite B>

[Provide a description of what test items are included in this suite]

1.3 <Test B.1>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

1.4 <Test B.2>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

1.5 <Test B.3>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

Section 3 : <Test Suite C>

[Provide a description of what test items are included in this suite]

1.6 <Test C.1>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

1.7 <Test C.2>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks

1.8

<Test C.3>

Test Case ID	Test Case Name	Summary	Expected UX	Remarks
<unique id to identify the test case>	<short name to identify the test case>	<brief summary of this test case>	<brief explanation of what the expected User Experience of this test case should be>	<any additional remarks>

ANNEX II : User Acceptance Test Review Report

Section 1 : Introduction

Ref. Sprint: XXXXXXXXXXXX

Date: yyyy-mm-dd

Section 2 : Notes

The blank Review log can be found in the following location:

...

Completed Review logs should be placed in the following location:

...

The list of all the Test Cases can be found in the following location:

...

Section 3 : Review Team

Name	Role	Document Sections
Xxxx Xxxx	Test lead, required reviewer	All
Another Test case designer in the team	Required Reviewer	All
Requirements Author	Optional reviewer	All
Software component designer	Optional reviewer	All

Report

Item	Reviewer	M/I /-	Ref. Test Case	Defect	Resolution
1.					
2.					
3.					
4.					
5.					
6.					
7.					
8.					
9.					
10.					
11.					
12.					
13.					
14.					
15.					
16.					

Notes:

- It is preferred but optional to classify defects as Major Defect (M), Issue (I), or Minor Defect (-). Only major defects and issues should be discussed at the review.
- Keep descriptions informative but short (no editorials, please). You can optionally propose a resolution.
- When identifying table and figure objects, specify the document section and then the object. Example: "1.2, Figure 4".
- Item numbers are automatically enumerated.
- If there is content missing from the document, add your suggestions at the end of the table.

ANNEX III : High-level Feedback from Stakeholders

Section 1 : Impact of Platform Output

A. Clinicians

1. How easy was it to understand the output provided by the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. How easy was it to explain the Platform's output to your patients?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. How would you rate the quality of information provided as output by the Platform?

Very poor Poor Fair Good Excellent

4. To what extent do you consider the Platform's output when caring for patients?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

5. Describe how you used the Platform's output while assessing and managing patients.

[Max 150 words]

B. Researchers

1. How easy was it to understand the output provided by the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. How would you rate the quality of information provided as output by the Platform?

Very poor Poor Fair Good Excellent

3. Are your experience using the Platform or your produced research findings useful towards the Platform's future development?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

4. Describe how you used the Platform outputs for research related activities.

[Max 150 words]

C. Patients

1. How easy was it to understand the output provided by the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. How trustworthy do you believe the Platform output to be?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Describe how the Platform output has had impact on your health, including deeper understanding of your health condition (e.g. diagnosis) and deciding on treatments.

[Max 150 words]

D. Caregivers

1. How easy was it to understand the output provided by the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. How trustworthy do you believe the Platform output to be when making caregiving decisions?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Describe how the Platform output has impacted your caregiving.

[Max 150 words]

Section 2 : Pilot implementation and Data Quality Assurance

A. Clinicians

1. How easy was it to implement the MES-CoBraD Pilot Protocol for multidisciplinary data acquisition?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. How easy was it to understand the type of data that should be acquired through the Pilot Protocol?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Was the content/data acquired meaningful for your activities?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

4. Did the content/data acquired impact your clinical decision?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

5. Which content/data would you remove from the Pilot Protocol (and why)?

[Max 150 words per item/content/data]

6. Which content/data would you add in the Pilot Protocol (and why)?

Max 150 words per item/content/data

7. How easy was it to manually enter data into the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely Not Applicable

8. Was the time required to manually enter the data into the Platform:

Comparatively short About right, given the task Too long Not Applicable

9. Are you concerned that it is easy to make mistakes entering data manually into the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

10. Please share any feedback regarding data quality assurance? [Max 150 words]

B. Researchers

1. How easy was it to implement the MES-CoBraD Pilot Protocol for multidisciplinary data acquisition?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. How easy was it to understand the type of data that should be acquired through the Pilot Protocol?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Was the content/data acquired meaningful for your activities?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Was the content/data acquired meaningful for your research activities?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

4. Did the content/data acquired impact your hypothesis testing and interpretation?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

5. Which content/data would you remove from the Pilot Protocol (and why)?

[Max 150 words per item/content/data]

6. Which content/data would you add in the Pilot Protocol (and why)?

Max 150 words per item/content/data

5. How easy was it to assess data quality (*note: you might consider completeness/missing values; identification of outlier or implausible values; trends or distributions in the data, etc.*)?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

6. What other information regarding data quality would you expect the platform to provide? [Max 150 words]

C. Patients and Caregivers

1. How easy was it to complete the MES-CoBraD Pilot Protocol?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. Do you believe you benefitted in obtaining a more accurate diagnosis and better management through the Pilot Protocol?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Is the Pilot Protocol time efficient for the amount of health information and quality of care you obtained?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

4. Do you consider the Pilot Protocol cost efficient for the amount of health information and quality of care you obtained?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

Section 3 : Analysis and use of modules

A. Clinicians

1. How accessible was Module [X] of the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

1. Was it easy to understand the purpose of Module [X]?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. Was it easy to understand the analysis report for Module [X]?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Did Module [X] perform what it was supposed to perform?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
4. Was the content of the analysis report by Module [X] useful for your clinical practice?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
5. How relevant to your daily clinical practice is the analysis provided by Module [X]?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
6. A. Did the analysis by Module [X] help you in your clinical decisions?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
- B. Please elaborate.
[free text max 300 words]
7. Did the use of Module [X] help you learn something new about your patient?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
8. Did the use of Module [X] help you save time in assessing a patient?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
9. Did the use of Module [X] help in reducing cost in assessing a patient?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
10. Did the use of Module [X] help you access information of vulnerable or underserved populations that would otherwise be difficult to obtain in an objective / feasible / ethical manner?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
11. Did the use of Module [X] help you develop new clinical hypotheses?
Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely
12. How could Module [X] be improved so that it can be more effective in clinical settings?

[free text max 300 words]

B. Researchers

1. How accessible was Module [X] of the Platform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. Was it easy to understand the purpose of Module [X]?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

3. Was it easy to understand the analysis report for Module [X]?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

4. Did Module [X] perform what it was supposed to perform?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

5. Was the content of the analysis report by Module [X] useful for your research?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

6. How relevant to your daily research activities is the analysis provided by Module [X]?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

7. A. Did the analysis by Module [X] help you in your research decisions?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. Please elaborate.

[free text max 300 words]

8. Did the use of Module [X] help you develop new knowledge in your field of research?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

9. Did the use of Module [X] help you save time in performing your research?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

10. Did the use of Module [X] help in reducing cost in performing your research?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

11. Did the use of Module [X] help you perform research on vulnerable or underserved populations in an efficient, accurate, and ethical manner?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

12. Did the use of Module [X] help you develop new research hypotheses?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

13. How could Module [X] be improved so that it can be more effective in research settings?

[free text max 300 words]

Section 4 : Interpretation of Analytical Results

A. CLINICIANS

1. How easy was it to understand the data interpretation based on the analytical results report?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. A. How complete was the report interpreting the analytical results?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. If you feel the report was incomplete, which additional features or explanations would you like the Platform to provide? [Free text max 300 words].

3. A. Did the data interpretation report provide the expected information to your clinical questions?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. If you feel the report was missing essential information, which additional information would you like the Platform to provide? [Free text max 300 words].

4. A. How much did your interpretation of the report impact your clinical decisions?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. Please, provide some examples. [Free text max 300 words].

5. A. How relevant was the content of the analysis interpretation report to your clinical practice?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. Please, provide some examples. [Free text max 300 words].

6. Did the data interpretation report help you learn something new about the clinical status of your patient?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

7. Did the data interpretation report help reduce costs in assessing your patients (e.g., avoided the request for additional unnecessary examinations)?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

8. Did the data interpretation report based on analytical results help develop new clinical hypotheses?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

9. How could the data interpretation report based on analytical results be improved? [Free text max 300 words].

B. RESEARCHERS

1. How understandable was the data interpretation based on the analytical results report?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

2. A. How complete was the data interpretation report based on the analytical results?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. If you feel the report was incomplete, which additional features or explanations would you like the system to provide? [Free text max 300 words].

3. A. Did the data interpretation report provide the expected information to your researchh questions?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. If you feel the report was missing information in this sense, which additional information would you like the system to provide? [Free text max 300 words].

4. A. How much did your interpretation of the report impact your research questions and hypotheses?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. Please, provide some examples. [Free text max 300 words].

5. A. How relevant was the data interpretation report in answering your research questions?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

B. Please, elaborate the answer above. [Free text max 300 words].

6. Did the data interpretation report help you acquire new insights to understanding your scientific field?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

7. Did the data interpretation report help you develop new research hypotheses?

Not at all Somewhat Moderately Significantly Extremely

8. How could the data interpretation report be improved in answering your research questions? [Free text max 300 words].

References

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- [AGILE] Agile Modeling (2019), <http://agilemodeling.com/essays/fdd.htm>, accessed in March 2019

